

**COLLEGE STUDENT'S ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND
ACADEMIC RESILIENCE IN THE CONTEXT OF THIS
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VISUAL ARTS PERFORMANCE**

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College Student's Achievement Motivation and Academic Resilience in the Context of this New Normal: Its Implications to their Visual Arts Performance

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Abstract

Motivation and resilience are necessary at this challenging time for students to thrive; hence, this study intended to determine if the college students' achievement motivation and academic resilience have implications on the performance of their visual art. A modified Achievement Motivation scale questionnaire from the constructs of Richard Lynn (1969) and a modified Academic Resilience Scale-30 (ARS-30) from the constructs of Simon Cassidy (2016) were utilized. Visual Arts Performance was determined on the basis of the creative works of art in terms of drawing, sculpting, and collage making. Descriptive correlational design was employed. To organize the data, descriptive statistics was employed to determine their level of achievement motivation, academic resilience, and art performance. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was utilized to measure the association between the participants' achievement motivation and their academic resilience. Multiple Regression was also employed to ascertain if the participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience significantly predict their visual arts performance. The study's findings show that the students' achievement motivation and academic resilience were high and their visual arts performance was very good. Moreover, the findings show that achievement motivation and academic resilience are significantly associated and these predicted the visual arts performance of the students in the context of this new normal. The researcher concludes that Achievement Motivation and Academic Resilience are significant predictors of visual arts performance. This study recommends that the university administrators may continue providing the instructors with opportunities to enhance their knowledge and awareness in developing students' achievement motivation and academic resilience.

Keywords: *achievement motivation, academic resilience, visual arts performance*

Introduction

Teachers always keep students motivated while not letting their morale down, especially in this new normal. Student motivation is shown as a relevant variable because it is related to students' learning goals, which, in turn, evoke different mental situations in students, resulting in them to having a positive or negative attitude toward their studies.

According to Robbins et al. (2004), Hattie (2009), Plante et al. (2013), and Wigfield et al. (2016), achievement motivation stimulates and controls action toward achievement and therefore is recognized to be a vital determinant of academic success. In addition, achievement motivation includes various constructs like motivational beliefs, task values, goals, and achievement motives and is not a single construct (Murphy and Alexander, 2000; Wigfield and Cambria, 2010; Wigfield et al., 2016). Hyde and Kling (2001) surmised that the increase in achievement motivation was probably caused by better opportunities to gain education and find employment. Similar findings were also reported by B. A. Greene and T. K. DeBacker (2004), who stated in their study that men and women differed more significantly in long-term goals and plans. Men mainly expressed plans concerning a career in sciences and technologies and gained prestige and good earnings.

Moreover, there are many studies that examined different motivational constructs in students' academic achievement specifically on students' cognitive abilities and prior achievement (Steinmayr and Spinath, 2009; Kriegbaum et al., 2015). A recent study conducted by Baños et al. (2020), presented a predictive model of academic performance based on the individual's satisfaction. This determines the effort invested to achieve learning and academic performance. Furthermore, a meta-analysis presented by Taylor et al. (2014) highlighted the role of motivation on school achievement; they found that self-determined motivation was associated with higher academic performance.

On another note, Martin (2002) explains that academic resilience has gained increasing attention in the school context due to its relation to positive achievement and school-related adjustment. In recent years, the association between resilience and education has received much attention in the social sciences. Despite the challenges, resilient students seem to successfully defeat stressful school-related conditions, maintain optimal levels of motivation, and gain high performance (Martin A.J., Marsh H.W. 2006, Romano L., Buonomo I., Callea A., 2019). In addition, the association between academic resilience and school engagement has been magnified in the previous studies, showing that they are strictly and positively related (e.g., Ahmed U., Umrani W.A., Qureshi M.A., Samad A., 2018).

Meanwhile, students who rely on personal resources when dealing with school tasks tend to drive all the efforts to enhance their energy, achieve their goals, dedication levels in daily activities and be more engaged than their peers (Salmela-Aro K., Upadyaya K., 2014, Schaufeli W.B., Salanova M., 2007). Similarly, individuals with progressive personal resources appear to pursue contextual resources to help them succeed and impact the way they recognize the environment and the social support they encounter (Lorente L. et al., 2014).

Alongside resilience, learner engagement is one more developing field of interest inside the global education domain that is the central construct of positive psychology (Yu et al., 2019; Han and Wang, 2021; Wang et al., 2021). The relation between resilience and learner engagement is reported in some studies, as students with low degrees of resilience also had low degrees of engagement (Pidgeon and Keye, 2014).

In the same manner, the academic resilience of students has been included in the study as an indicator, with the expectation that it will affect students' academic performance. For instance, a study investigated the effects of self-esteem and resilience factors on the academic performance of international students among Australian students. Their findings indicated that self-esteem and endurance are significant predictors of academic performance in both categories (Kwek et al., 2013).

Moreover, resilience is generally considered a strength or asset, a desirable and advantageous quality, likely to positively impact aspects of an individual's performance, achievement, health, and wellbeing (Bartley et al., 2010). Also, Martin and Marsh (2009), for instance, refer to their approach to academic resilience as an inherently asset-oriented, strength-based, and aspirational approach to students' response to academic adversity. The benefits of academic resilience are demonstrated by studies that report resilience as a significant predictor of coping in a university life (McLafferty et al., 2012). Furthermore, there is a positive relationship between academic resilience and academic achievement (Fallon, 2010) which suggests the potential to foster increased resilience through interventions (Gardynik, 2008). Moreover, such interventions yielded to positive effects which incorporates aspects of academic resilience (Martin and Marsh, 2008).

In art performance, people may learn to address and embrace diversity, present emotions, and differentiate values in the world. Art Education allows schools to provide the students with knowledge of ethics, see social realities and understand their rights and responsibilities. Considering the foregoing constructs, this investigation aimed to determine if the college students' achievement motivation and academic resilience are associated and, in turn, influenced the performance of their visual arts performance in the context of this new normal.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine if college students' achievement motivation and academic resilience in this new normal affect the performance of their visual art. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the participants' level of achievement motivation?
2. What is the participants' level of academic resilience?
3. What is the participants' performance in visual arts?
4. Is the participants' achievement motivation significantly associated with their academic resilience?
5. Do the participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience significantly predict their performance in visual arts?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlational method of research. Correlation research examines various factors, including the relationship of two or more variables and the theoretical model that might be developed or verified to explain these resultant correlations (Matud, 2004). The researcher found this research design as deemed appropriate for the study intended to determine the relationship between the college students' achievement motivation and academic resilience in the context of this new normal and to find out whether these two variables influence the participants' visual arts performance.

Respondents

The study participants were the fifty-four (54) college students from the first-year level in one of the campuses of a satellite university in Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines, enrolled for the Academic Year 2021-2022. These students were from the following programs: Bachelor of Agricultural Technology and Bachelor of Science in Information Technology. Each participant had three (3) performance tasks to accomplish that were scored by the instructor and two (2) other instructors who served as inter-raters with scoring criteria to measure the performance of their visual arts.

Instrument

This study utilized two questionnaires that were contextualized into the flexible learning modality. To determine the participants' level of achievement motivation, a modified Achievement Motivation scale questionnaire from the constructs of Richard Lynn (1969) was utilized consisting of seventeen (17) items. Furthermore, to determine the level of academic resilience, a modified Academic Resilience Scale-30 (ARS-30) questionnaire that consists of twenty-five (25) items from the constructs of Simon Cassidy (2016) was also utilized. The two questionnaires used a Likert- scale from very high (5) to very low (1). Moreover, visual arts performance was determined on the basis of the three creative works of art: drawing, sculpting, and collage making.

The questionnaires used in the study were subjected to content validation by the panelists and field experts. Their comments and suggestions were incorporated into the final paper. The research instruments were pilot-tested to thirty (30) college students who were

not the participants of the study in order to test the reliability of the items on one of the campuses of a university satellite in Cagayan de Oro City Philippines.

Cronbach's coefficient alpha was used to test the reliability of the items. The items under Achievement Motivation got a Cronbach alpha of .771, and the items under Academic Resilience got a Cronbach alpha of .830.

Gliem and Gliem (2003) cited that the closer the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to 1.0, the greater its internal consistency, specifically from 0.7 to 1.0. The values showed the reliability and internal consistency of the instruments' items in measuring the study's variables; thus, the items were considered highly reliable.

Procedure

Before conducting the research study, the researcher sought the school's Research and Ethics Committee's (REC) approval, following all the suggestions made by the panel during the research proposal. After that, the researcher asked for the University President's permission to perform the study in all participating programs and subjects. Upon approval, the researcher asked for the students' email addresses since the questionnaires were administered via Google form.

A letter together with the informed consent and questionnaires were sent via email to the participants. The Informed Consent form was used since the participants in the study were of legal age. Also, the participants were assured of the anonymity and privacy of the data gathered. As stated in RA 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal data must be collected for valid reasons. Both parties giving and receiving information are made aware of it. The right to participate or withdraw from the study was enclosed, which was in the first part. A link to the Google form was indicated in the letter to access the survey questionnaires. In case the participants cannot make it through online, the researcher provided a hard copy of the informed consent along with the survey questionnaires.

The participants received a notification if the questionnaire was already sent through their emails. They were also informed to accomplish the survey during their free working hours. Only the researcher has access to the google form's main program and the collected data to ensure privacy.

Furthermore, the participants did not receive any payment, and their answers do not affect their current or future status at the university. In addition, the participants were given information about the research being conducted. They were informed that by participating in the study, they were made aware of the significance of their achievement motivation and academic resilience in relation to visual arts performance during this time of the pandemic. After the completion of the study, the collected data were discarded after they had served their purpose.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the data, the following statistical tools were used:

Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were employed to describe the participants' level of achievement motivation, academic resilience, and visual arts performance in Problems 1, 2, and 3. While in Problem 4, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was utilized to measure the association between the participants' achievement motivation to their academic resilience. Furthermore, Problem 5 utilized Multiple Regression Analysis to determine if the participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience significantly predict the performance in visual arts.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data. The presentation follows the order and sequence of problem statements.

Problem 1. What is the participants' level of achievement motivation?

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' level of achievement motivation. The data show that the student's level of achievement motivation was high, as indicated in the overall mean of 3.73. This means that the participants had a strong belief in their ability or capacity to do the tasks expected of them in their performance.

Table 1. *Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Achievement Motivation*

<i>Range</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
4.51-5.00	Very High	2	3.70
3.51-4.50	High	39	72.22
2.51-3.50	Moderate	13	24.07
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.00
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		54	100.0
Overall Mean			3.73
Interpretation			High
SD			0.41

This is further supported by 39 or 72.22 percent of them who claimed to have a high level of achievement motivation, and 2 or 3.70 percent cited they had very high achievement motivation. It is also worth mentioning that there is 13 or 24.07 percent expressed to have only moderate achievement motivation. The researcher believes that the findings validate the importance of achievement-motivation in fostering great outcomes.

Gleaning further from the table, the figures show that the participants have a high ability to accept the risks in the pursuit of their career ($M=4.46$) as the indicator that got the highest. This was followed by their ability to do hard work in the right place at the right time ($M=4.28$) and their capacity to avoid conflict ($M=4.28$). Next was their ability to be independent ($M=4.19$) and their capability to spend much time working alone ($M=4.19$). On the other hand, the lowest indicator from the reversely scored items was their capability to rethink plans when they knew that others disapproved of their actions ($M=1.94$), and this was followed by their ability to dislike entering a room full of strangers and trying to connect ($M= 2.54$) and on their capability of being a competitive person and compete for the sake of competing ($M= 3.15$). The result implies that students with low achievement motivation have difficulty improving their performance in visual arts no matter how good the teacher, curriculum, or university is. Furthermore, unmotivated students can disengage other students from academics, which can affect the environment of an entire classroom.

Problem 2. What is the participants' level of academic resilience?

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' level of academic resilience. The data show that the student's level of academic resilience was generally high, as indicated in the overall mean of 4.11. This means that the participants had a strong ability or capacity to accept any challenges and feedback from the instructor in order to produce creative artworks during the time of the pandemic.

Table 2. *Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Academic Resilience*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	11	20.37
3.51-4.50	High	38	70.37
2.51-3.50	Moderate	4	7.41
1.51-2.50	Low	1	1.85
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		54	100.0
Overall Mean		4.11	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.48	

Noticeably, out of 54 student-participants, 38 or 70.37 percent of them had a high level of academic resilience, and 11 or 20.37 percent of them showed a very high level of academic resilience. The data may imply that the participants have a high sense of academic resiliency while remaining calm in the midst of difficulties and facing stressful situations in the new normal.

As to the indicators of academic resilience, having a very high level of accepting the instructor's feedback to improve work ($M = 4.72$) yielded the highest and followed by their ability to readily accept the instructor's feedback ($M = 4.69$), and on their ability to see life's situation as a challenge ($M= 4.5$) having a high level. Furthermore, on their ability to stop thinking negative thoughts ($M= 4.46$) and on their ability to consider every situation that comes along with life and motivate themselves ($M= 4.43$). In contrast, having a moderate level of their ability to think chances of success at university were poor ($M= 3.35$) yielded the lowest and their ability not to panic ($M= 3.43$). In addition, their ability to get annoyed when they received some activities ($M= 3.44$) had a moderate level of academic resilience as the reversely scored item. It is remarkable that college students were academically resilient in accepting the instructors' feedback to improve their work without any complaints and avoid any conflict to do their work on time during the time of pandemics and uncertainty.

Problem 3. What is the performance of the participants in visual arts?

Table 3. *Descriptive Statistics on the Participants' Visual Arts Performance*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
65 -75	Outstanding	31	57.41
47 - 64.99	Very Good	23	42.59
29 - 46.99	Good	0	0
11 - 28.99	Fair	0	0
1 - 10.99	Poor	0	0
Total		54	100.00
Overall Mean		64.83	
Description		Very Good	
Standard Deviation		3.36	

Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics of the participants' performance in visual arts in terms of drawing, sculpting, and collage making.

Generally, the participants had very good performance in visual arts, as indicated in an overall mean of 64.83. This further implies that the students can perform well in their visual arts outputs. Moreover, the figures reveal that 31 or 57.41 percent of them had outstanding visual arts performance, while 23 or 42.59 percent of them had very good performance in the criteria of content, creativity, and relevance.

Furthermore, when students are able to perform tasks successfully and get good grades, they will be motivated and willing to put more effort into their work (Bainbridge, 2011). "The arts are a fundamentally important part of the culture, and an education without them is an impoverished education leading to an impoverished society. Studying the arts should not have to be justified in terms of anything else" (Hetland & Winner, 2001). Visual arts, such as drawing and soft sculpture, also enhance writing skills by encouraging creative thinking (Richardson, Sacks, & Ayers, 2003).

Problem 4. Is the participants' achievement motivation significantly associated with their academic resilience?

Ho1. The participants' achievement motivation is not significantly associated with their academic resilience.

The results of correlation between achievement motivation and academic resilience are presented in Table 4. From the figures, it revealed that academic resilience is positively correlated with achievement motivation (.644) and the correlation is significant at the .01 level.

Table 4. Correlation Results of Achievement Motivation and Academic Resilience

Academic Resilience	Measures	
	Pearson Correlation	Achievement Motivation
		.644**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

***Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

There is sufficient evidence that achievement motivation is significantly associated with academic resilience; hence, the null hypothesis can be rejected. From the findings of this study, the participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience are significantly associated. This implies that motivated students sustain a high level of academic resilience despite the existence of stressful events at school.

The findings concur with the studies of Kim and Lee (2014) that demotivated ESL learners, in comparison with the motivated ones, revealed low resilience levels. Despite different constructs, motivation plays the role of mediator in the process of being resilient (Resnick et al., 2018). The researcher infers that the energy and drive to learn, work effectively, and achieve one's potential is not sufficient to deal with academic setbacks or excessive study pressure and stress. Without some level of resilience to these types of challenges, the motivated student's gains may well be lost.

Problem 5. Do the participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience significantly influence their visual arts performance?

Ho2. The participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience do not significantly influence their visual arts performance.

Table 5 presents the regression analysis of the influence of achievement motivation and academic resilience on the participants' visual arts performance.

Table 5. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Achievement Motivation and Academic Resilience on Performance in Art Appreciation

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	63.31	2.75		23.02	.000
Achievement Motivation	2.16	.797	.265	2.72**	.009
Academic Resilience	4.48	.684	.638	6.55**	.000
Model Summary					
R = .815	R ² = .664	Adjusted R ² = .651	F = 50.496**	p = .000	

***significant at 0.01 level*

Findings reveal that the whole model is significant (F=50.496, p=.000) with 65.1 percent of the variability in their performance as being accounted for by a combination of achievement motivation and academic resilience. Thus, the null hypothesis can be rejected.

Data show that as a whole, the participants' achievement motivation and academic resilience predict their performance in visual arts. Hence, the whole model supported the researcher's assumption that the more academically motivated and highly resilient the students are, the higher their performance in visual arts.

Specifically, achievement motivation as a predictor of the performance (t=2.72**, p=.009) indicating that for every unit increase in the participants' achievement motivation, there is a corresponding 2.16 increase in their performance. The results find resonance with what Busato, Prins, Elshout, and Hamaker (2000) found that intellectual ability and achievement motivation are positively associated with

academic success. In fact, other reasons for the high academic success of high ability students are their high level of motivation to continue their education (Kozochkina, 2009), their high intellectual ability, verbal ability, attribution of failure to stable factors and mood, academic self-concepts, attainment value, rehearsal, time management, and effort management than low ability students (Lau & Chan, 2001).

Similarly, the findings reveal that academic resilience is a predictor of performance ($t=6.55^{**}$, $p=.000$), indicating that for every unit increase in the participants' academic resilience, there is a corresponding 4.48 increase in their performance. This implies that highly resilient students would produce good Art output. The findings of the study are in line with the findings of Oke et al. (2016), which revealed that across all the groups studied, academic resilience was significantly correlated with academic achievement. Additionally, Mwangi, Okatcha, Kinai, and Ileri (2015) posited that resilience could significantly affect school and life outcomes for students, including academic achievement. Resilient students sustain high levels of achievement and performance despite the presence of stressful events and conditions.

Students who participate in arts learning experiences often improve their achievement in other realms of learning and life. In a well-documented national study using a federal database of over 25,000 middle and high school students, researchers from the University of California at Los Angeles found students with high arts involvement performed better on standardized achievement tests than students with low arts involvement. Moreover, the high arts-involved students also watched fewer hours of TV, participated in more community service, and reported less boredom in school (Catterall, James S., 2002).

Furthermore, the findings of the study of Rebecca E.C, et al (2021) revealed that achievement scores in chemistry are significantly related to motivation as well as academic resilience. Achievement in chemistry was also a significant co-predicted by motivation and academic resilience.

In other words, the results of this research show that a high level of achievement, motivation and academic resilience affect performance in visual arts. Moreover, the results of this research are in line with those of Bye, Pushkar, and Conway (2007), Eom, Wen, and Ashill (2006), and Muller & Louw (2004), in which learning interest and motivation, either separately or simultaneously had an influence on students' learning outcomes in various subjects and contexts. The researcher believes that the student's level of achievement, motivation and academic resilience have a huge impact on the performance of their visual art during this time of the pandemic.

Conclusions

The researcher's assumption of this study was confirmed that Achievement Motivation and Academic Resilience are significant predictors of visual arts performance. If a student lacks motivation, he is unlikely to achieve success no matter who the teacher is or what the curricula are, whereas the highly motivated students can succeed in whatever conditions.

The more efforts they make, the more fruits they will reap. High achievers are good at carrying out a plan about realizing the aim of language. Moreover, they could persist in carrying out their plans. With their scores in exams getting higher, the high achievers may get a sense of achievement more frequently, and they are more internally motivated to learn. (Lai Xuefang, 2005).

The theory of David McClelland (1961) on achievement motivation and the theory of Micheal Rutter (2006) on resilience which are the basis for this study, confirmed the idea that being motivated would lead to better performance. Furthermore, arts have long been considered part of the human affective experience and needed by our young people as a medium for safe expression, communication, exploration, imagination, and cultural and historical understanding. Thus, the challenge for Visual Arts integration should not focus only on a particular art discipline alone, like Humanities (Art Appreciation) somewhat; it should extend across the curriculum. Moreover, both achievement motivation and academic resilience have a vital role in college students' visual arts performance.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

That the university administrators may continue providing the college instructors with development sessions that would enhance their knowledge and awareness on how to develop from among the students their achievement motivation and academic resilience;

That the university system may bring local artists and teachers into partnerships so that they could develop arts integration and creative teaching strategies in conducting visual arts-related activities;

That the faculty may ensure the continuous quality programs related to visual art integration and use of visual arts in teaching Humanities (Art Appreciation);

That researchers may conduct similar research with a larger number of participants and with different academic levels.

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